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THE PERSPECTIVES OF USING FORTIFIED FOOD PRODUCTS IN SPORTSMEN

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Abstract. Today, the main priority of athletes' nutrition is to provide them with high quality food products. High quality food products contribute to their health: affect growth and physical development, alter their ability to work, improve life expectancy and adaptability. To provide athletes with complete food products, we provide perspectives for the use of fortified foods in them. The main micronutrient involved in fortification - selenium, which is a key vital element, has been selected. It regulates the most important vital processes: these are metabolic processes, the work of skeletal muscle and muscle fibers of internal organs. Selenium has been studied to maximize the enzymatic activity of selenium-dependent enzyme glutathione peroxidase and its enzyme group. Maximum antioxidant protection of the athlete's body using these processes has been shown. Opinions are expressed about the conditions for taking multivitamin preparations for athletes.

Keywords: athlete, enzyme, fortification, food, antioxidant, multivitamins.

Introduction. In all over the world, as well as in our country, one of the main priorities is to provide the population with high quality food products. High quality foods contribute to human health. Affects growth and physical development. Changes human labour capacity, improves the life expectancy and adaptive capabilities of the population. Foods are mostly rich in minerals. Minerals are included in the composition of any living organism ^[1]. Included in the composition of enzymes, hormones. Minerals are found in the human body in the form of food and water. The chemical elements that are found in the body in small quantities are called micronutrients. It is true that they have no nutritional value compared to proteins, fats and carbohydrates, but their role is very important for the proper management of biochemical processes in living organisms. Selenium is especially important in the fortification of food products from micronutrients ^[6].

Aim and objectives of the research. The aim of the research was to find the available material about the food used by athletes for sports, fortified with micronutrients. We studied the advantages of the micronutrient used in fortification compared to other elements. We had to compare them according to their use and demand in the world market. Relate them to the nutritional status of athletes and draw appropriate conclusions based on the analysis.

Materials and methods. We have found relevant material about fortified foods. We also found material on the major micronutrients involved in fortification.

Discussion of the results of the research. We first learned why we prefer Selenium-fortified foods in athlete's foods. Selenium is an essential micronutrient for life. Found in human, animal and plant organisms. The highest concentrations of Selenium are found in the liver and kidneys. The average Selenium concentration in adults is 15 mg. Selenium affects the metabolism and toxicity of some drugs and chemicals. The toxicity of some compounds in organisms is enhanced by a lack of Selenium. The recommended daily allowance for Selenium is 0.07 mg. Because the

microelement Selenium belongs to the group of vital elements, it regulates the most important vital processes. These are metabolic processes, the work of skeletal muscle and muscle fibers of internal organs. It is also important to remember that its action is related to the activity of other regulators in the body, such as iodine, antioxidant vitamins E, A, C. The most important mechanisms of the protective action of Selenium on our body ^[3] are well studied: immunostimulatory and anti-tumor effect, detoxification of heavy metals, radioprotective effect. With Selenium deficiency, i.e. when the Selenium content in the body falls below a certain critical level, all defense systems begin to work in a weakened mode, leading to the emergence of various disorders and diseases. The role of Selenium in the work of myocardial cells is important. These are unique cells that have no analogues. Throughout their lives they complete a continuous cycle of heartbeats. It is a very reliable mechanism in which enzymes containing Selenium play an important role. The most important function of Selenium is to transmit hereditary information it plays an important role in the functioning of the human reproductive organs. A small deficiency of Selenium will turn into a significant deficiency of Selenium for the whole organism, namely for myocardial cells and skeletal muscle cells.

We agree that Selenium regulates the absorption and metabolism of vitamins A, C, E and K in living organisms. But we have a different view of some scientists: that athletes are offered multivitamins before intense exercise or competition. We believe that multivitamin preparations are mainly composed of water and fat soluble vitamins ^[2]. That water and fat soluble vitamins have a different intake and its intake to not cause any discomfort to the athletes before starting intense training or competition.

The microelement Selenium maximally regulates the activity of glutathione peroxidase, one of the most potent and major antioxidant enzymes ^[4]. We know that antioxidants are a group of certain compounds that inhibit or weaken the oxidation process of other molecules and therefore slow down the so-called. The formation of "free radicals" that damage cells. Cell damage leads to the development of adverse biochemical reactions in the body ^[5]. The weakening of the antioxidant system is mainly manifested by a sharp decrease in the activity of endogenous enzymes: superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase, glutathione peroxidase, glutathione reductase) and the accumulation of peroxidation products ^[7].

In mitochondria, there are mainly oxidative processes and the enhancement of superoxidation processes is accompanied by disruption of mitochondrial function and improper biochemical-physiological processes. In addition to the ability to deactivate these properties: free radicals, peroxides, electrophilic and carcinogenic compounds, Selenium can stimulate the conversion of methionine to cysteine. The latter promotes the synthesis of glutathione and increases the antioxidant properties of the body. Important forms of Selenium are: selenocysteine and selenomethionine.

Selenomethionine is found in various proteins instead of methionine. Selenocysteine is synthesized in humans and animals. It is involved in the activation of glutathione peroxidase and its group of enzymes and provides antioxidant protection to the lipid region of the cell. The traditional view of athlete nutrition is that athletes consume more nutrients than ordinary people

who do not exercise. In fact, this view is completely justified by athletes, as they require more food to meet the increased amount of fuel (energy) needed during exercise.

The use of compounds containing the low molecular weight thiol group before physical activity in athletes prevents the rapid uptake of endogenous sulfide groups into enzymes and proteins. This is one of the experiments proven to increase muscle work and enhance the oxidation reactions of free radicals, to prevent harmful effects.

Based on the analysis and research of the studied literary material, we can make the following conclusions:

1. It is essential for athletes under physical activity to use fortified foods.
2. It is desirable to use the microelement Selenium in food fortification.
3. The studied micronutrient Selenium is considered as an essential micronutrient for athletes.
4. The microelement Selenium maximally regulates the activity of glutathione peroxidase, one of the powerful and main antioxidant enzyme.
5. Glutathione peroxidase provides maximum antioxidant defense of the body of athletes.
6. It is advisable to reconsider the conditions for taking multivitamin preparations for athletes.

Conclusion

Today, the main priority of athletes' nutrition is to provide them with high quality food products. High quality food products contribute to their health: affect growth and physical development, alter their ability to work, improve life expectancy and adaptability. To provide athletes with complete food products, we provide perspectives for the use of fortified foods in them. The main micronutrient involved in fortification - selenium, which is a key vital element, has been selected. It regulates the most important vital processes: these are metabolic processes, the work of skeletal muscle and muscle fibers of internal organs. Selenium has been studied to maximize the enzymatic activity of selenium-dependent enzyme glutathione peroxidase and its enzyme group. Maximum antioxidant protection of the athlete's body using these processes has been shown. Opinions are expressed about the conditions for taking multivitamin preparations for athletes.

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